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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF MUTATIONS IN THE INTERLEUKIN-1B GENE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ATONIC POSTPARTUM HEMORRHAGE.....10

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MEDICAL AND PROPHYLACTIC TECHNOLOGIES OF MONITORING OF ATMOSPHERIC AIR POLLUTION BY CHEMICAL POLLUTANTS AND ISSUES OF STUDYING THE PATHOGENESIS OF DISEASES OF THE POPULATION ASSOCIATED WITH EXPOSURE TO ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS.....17
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THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF TRANSFORMATION OF TRAINING, RETRAINING AND CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION OF MANAGERS IN THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....23

THERAPY

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COMPREHENSIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE CURRENT EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION REGARDING THE INCIDENCE AND PREVALENCE OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE(LITERARY REVIEW).....30

SURGERY

5. **Arziev A Ismoil, Mamanov Ch Muxammad., Arzieva B Gulnora.**
DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TACTICS FOR COMPLICATED FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....36
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POSSIBILITIES OF MODERIN RADIATION METODS IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS AND ITS COMPLICATIONS.....44
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CLINICAL RATIONALE FOR MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTIONS IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS WITH A HIGH RISK OF SURGERY AND ANESTHESIA.....52
8. **Pakirdinov S. Alisher, Nuritdinov T. Arifjon., Temirov Ch. Pulat.**
SURGICAL TREATMENT OF MEDIAGASTRIC ULCERS.....62
9. **Ikramova D. Farida, Musashaykhov T. Khusanbay.**
ANTISEPTICS IN THE TREATMENT OF PURULENT COMPLICATIONS AFTER ABDOMINAL OPERATIONS.....70
10. **Ruziboyev A. Sanjar, Sadikov A. Rustam. Allaberdiev A. Ne'mat.**
EFFICIENCY COMPARISON OF A MODIFIED METHOD FOR ALLOPLASTY OF INGUINAL HERNIA IN AN EXPERIMENTAL.....75
11. **Musashaykhov T. Khusanbay, Ikramova D. Farida, Musashaykhov Kh. Umidjon.**
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PUTUROUS DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES.....83
12. **Ahmedov K. Gayrat, Tashkenbayev R. Firdavs, Gulamov M. Olimjon, Toirov S. Abduxomit.**
BARIATRIC SURGERY AND THEIR COMPLICATIONS.....91

13. **Khursanov E. Yokub, Makhmudov B. Saydinjon, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar.**
MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF NON-TENSIONED HERNIOPLASTY FOR UMBILICAL HERNIA.....100
14. **ABDUVALIEVA M. Chulpanoy, KADIROV Z. Komiljon, KHALILOV K. Shukrullo**
A NUMBER OF ERRORS IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF ACUTE APPENDICITIS IN CHILDREN.....109

CHILDREN SURGERY

15. **Khalilov K. Shukrullo, Abduvalieva M. Chulpanoy, Kadirov Z. Komiljon.**
TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF DUODENAL ULCER DISEASE IN CHILDREN.115

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

16. **Eshonkulov T. Golibjon.**
FUNCTIONAL DISORDERS AND THEIR PREVENTION IN DENTAL DISEASES.....120
17. **Hojiyev H. Xurshid.**
THE ROLE OF PATHOGENETIC FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHRONIC APICAL PERIODONTITIS.....125
18. **Rizaev A. Eler, Khasanov K. Fazyl.**
THE RESULTS OF STUDIES OF THE STATE OF ANS IN PATIENTS WITH GLOSSODYNIA.....131
19. **Turaeva A. Firuza.**
IMMUNOBIOCHEMICAL MARKERS IN PATIENTS WITH GENERALIZED PARODONTITIS.....136
20. **Bekjanova E. Olga, Olimdjonov J. Kamron.**
MECHANISMS OF COMORBIDITY OF PERIODONTITIS AND INFLAMMATORY BOWEL PATHOLOGY.....144
21. **Badriddinov B. Baxrom.**
INDICATIONS FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS AND ORTHODONTIC EXAMINATION OF HIGH JAW PROTRUSIONS IN CHILDREN.....151
22. **Eshonkulov Sh.B.**
THE EFFECT OF ANTIBACTERIAL PHOTODYNAMIC THERAPY ON THE SENSITIVITY OF MICROBES ISOLATED FROM YOUNG CHILDREN WITH PURULENT-INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION.....160
23. **Idiyev E. Gayrat, Rakhimov Sh. Shokhrukh.**
INDICATIONS FOR DETERMINING THE CONDITION OF THE ORAL ORGANS IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS.....166
24. **Fattakhov A. Ravshan, Nuritdinov A. Ulugbek.**
DISC DISLOCATIONS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINTS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....171

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

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SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL ATRESIA OF THE EXTERNAL AUDITORY CANAL IN CHILDREN.....177
26. **Gulyamov B. Sherzod., Karabaev E. Khurram., Khamrakulova O. Nargiza.**
DIAGNOSIS OF CONGENITAL ANOMALIES OF THE EXTERNAL AND MIDDLE EAR IN CHILDREN.....190

27. **NASRETDINOVA T. Makhzuna., OMONOVA Sh. Maftuna**
SURUNKALI POLIPOZ RINOSINUSITLARNI DAVOSINI
OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....199

PEDIATRICS

28. **Kadirov Z. Komiljon, Abduvalieva M. Chulpanoy, Khalilov K. Shukrullo.**
ACUTE PURULENT DESTRUCTIVE PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN.....205

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

29. **Khakimova Z. Sakhiba, Khamdamova K., Bektashev B. Rakhmatullo, Abdullayeva Z. Kamola.**
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF LIQUORODYNAMIC DISTURBANCES IN THE
PATHOGENESIS OF DISCIRCULATORY ENCEPHALOPATHY 380.....211
30. **Yanova U. Elvira.**
ASSESSMENT OF CIRCULATORY DISORDERS IN THE VERTEBROBASILAR ZONE
IN KIMMERLE ANOMALY.....217

ANESTEZIOLOGY

31. **Nematulloev K. Tukhtasin , G'oyibov S. Salim.**
THE INFLUENCE OF SPINAL ANESTHESIA ON THE PROLONGATION OF THE QT
INTERVAL IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS.....226
32. **Sadikova A.Minura.**
THE QUESTION OF CHOOSING THE OPTIMAL OPTION OF ANESTHESIOLOGICAL
MANAGEMENT WHEN CARRYING OUT RECONSTRUCTIVE PLASTIC SURGERY IN
PATIENTS WITH POST-CLEAR CONTRACTURES OF THE FACE, NECK AND
CHEST.....233
33. **Sadikova A.Minura.**
ALGORITHM FOR MAINTAINING AIRWAY PATESTITV FOR VARIOUS CLINICAL
SITUATIONS RELATED TO CONTRACTURES NECK DURING OPERATIVE
INTERVENTIONS IN RECONSTRUCTIVE PLASTIC SURGERY.....240

ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY

34. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Ulmasov G. Firdavs, Rakhimov Kh. Zhakhongir.**
BRONCHOPULMONARY COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH LARYNGEAL
CANCER.....248
35. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Ulmasov G. Firdavs, Rakhimov Kh. Zhakhongir.**
CLINICO-MORPHOLOGICAL GROUPING OF BENIGN TUMOURS, CYSTS,
GYPERPLASTIC AND DYSTROPHIC TUMOUR-LIKE DISEASESOF THE
LARYNX.....254
36. **Ruziboyev A. Sanjar, Nosirov B. Akhtam, Amonov R. Ravshanovich.**
RESULTS OF TREATMENT WITH ACUTE GASTRIC BLEEDING DUE TO STOMACH
TUMORS.....261
37. **Zhumanov E. Ziyadulla, Khamidov A. Obid, Gaybullayev O, Sherzod.**
MORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF FIBROBLASTIC MENINGIOMA OF THE BRAIN
DETERMINED BY MAGNETIC RESONANCE TOMOGRAPHY EXAMINATION.....268
38. **Khamidov A. Obid, Zhumanov E. Ziyadulla, Beknazarova N, Xolniso.**
MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF XANTHOGRANULEMATOSIS CHOLECYSTITIS
DETERMINED BY ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION.....274

39. **Ametova S. Alie, Khodjibekova M. Yulduz, Ziyadullaev Kh. Shukhrat.**
ULTRASOUND PATTERNS INDICATING OSTEOCHONDRAL CHANGES IN MEDIUM AND SMALL JOINTS OF THE EXTREMITIES VARY AMONG THE PRIMARY TYPES OF ARTHROPATHY.....280

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

40. **Khudoykulova V. Farida, Kalonov S. Sohibjon.**
THE ROLE OF LIFESTYLE MODIFICATION AND EATING HABITS IN NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEAS.....291

MORPHOLOGY

41. **Oripov S. Firdavs, Togayeva S. Gulnora.**
REACTIVE CHANGES IN THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE PANCREAS IN VARIOUS PATHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS OF ORGANS AND SYSTEMS OF THE BODY (REVIEW ARTICLE).....299
42. **Kuliyev A. Azad, Karabaev G. Aminjon.**
A POINT ASSESSMENT OF THE GENERAL CONDITION OF RATS THAT SUFFERED A 10-MINUTE CLINICAL DEATH.....311
43. **Kuliyev A. Azad, Karabaev G. Aminjon.**
DYNAMICS OF CHANGES IN THE RELATIONSHIP OF HORMONES OF THE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM OF FEMALE RATS IN THE POST-INTENSIVE CARE PERIOD, AFTER MODELING A 10-MINUTE CLINICAL DEATH.....317
44. **Khamidova M. Farida, Ismailov M. Jasur, Sulaymanova J. Mariya.**
PATHOMORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE LARRYNGE UNDER NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS IN EXPERIMENTAL LARYNGITIS.....324
45. **Radjabov B. Akhtam.**
MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF MALES IN POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS AND IN CHRONIC ALCOHOLISM.....334
46. **Khamidova M. Farida, Yakubov Z. Munis.**
TRANSFORMATION OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE ARTIFICIAL VAGINA CREATED FROM THE LARGE INTESTINE.....339
47. **Urunova A. Mashxura, Pirmatov V. Salikh, Sadullayev E. Sadikjon.**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN MYOCARDIAL STRUCTURE DURING DEATH OF PREMATURE DICHORIAL DIAMNIOTIC TWINS.....349
48. **Toshmamatov N. Bakhtiyor, Djumanova E. Nargiza.**
CHANGES IN THE MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF THE GASTRIC MUCOSA AND THE BASE OF THE GASTRIC MUCOSA OF WHITE RATS IN POLYPRAGMAZY.....355
49. **Ismailova A. Jadida, Ermekbaeva U. Arkbal, Zinatdinova K. Indira.**
STUDY OF MORPHOLOGICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF EOSINOPHILIC ESOPHAGITIS.....361

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

50. **Makhkamov N.J., Nazarov I.R.**
CLINICAL-MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE AVASCULAR NECROSIS OF THE SON SUEBEA AFFECTED BY COVID-19.....367
51. **Tilyakov A. Xasan, Tilyakov B. Aziz, Temurov A. Alisher, Shukurov N. Fayzullakhon.**
EXPERIENCE IN PERFORMING OPERATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH A FRACTURE OF THE PROXIMAL FEMUR WITH A RISK OF DEEP VEIN THROMBOSIS.....372

52. **Husainboev D. Shokhrukhbek.**
SYMPTOMS, ETIOLOGY AND TYPES OF TREATMENT OF SHOULDER JOINT
INJURY INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....379

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

53. **Turonov S. Bobur, Iskandarova A. Malika.**
IRIDOLOGY AS A PROMISING DIAGNOSTIC METHOD IN CLINICAL PRACTICE
AND FORENSIC MEDICINE (LITERATURE REVIEW).....385
54. **Turonov S. Bobur, Iskandarov I. Alisher.**
VISCERO-IRIDAL REFLEX CONNECTIONS IN THE MECHANISM OF IRIDOLOGY
VISCERO-IRIDAL REFLEX CONNECTIONS IN THE MECHANISM OF
IRIDOLOGY.....391
55. **Indiaminov I. Sayit, Kamalov Sh. Sherzod.**
CURRENT STATE OF FORENSIC MEDICAL DIAGNOSTICS OF INJURIES RESULTING
FROM FALLS FROM A MOVING VEHICLE (LITERATURE REVIEW).....396

ENDOCRINOLOGY

56. **Kholikova O. Adliya, Halimova Yu. Zamira, Mavlyanova U. Gulkhida, Negmatova Sh. Gulzoda.**
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF DIAGNOSTIC RESULTS IN PATIENTS WITH
ACROMEGALY ACCORDING TO THE REGISTRY DATA.....403

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

57. **Dzhumaeva S. Nasiba, Karamatullaeva E. Zebo.**
CONSEQUENCES OF MUMPS INFECTION IN ADULTS (BASED ON THE EXAMPLE
OF SAMARKAND REGION).....412
58. **Samibaeva Kh. Umida.**
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN THE NEW
CORONAVIRUS INFECTION COVID-19 (LITERATURE REVIEW).....420
59. **Yarmuxamedova K. Mahbuba, Yakubova S. Nigina, Kuchkarova A. Shirina, Baymirzaev I. Abdusodik.**
CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MEASLES IN THE
SAMARKAND REGION.....428

OPHTHALMOLOGY

60. **Allayarov T. Azimbek, Rizaev A. Jasur, Yusupov A. Amin.**
ASSESSMENT OF STATISTICAL DATA ON DIABETIC RETINOPATHY IN
SAMARKAND.....434

UROLOGY

61. **Gafarov R. Rushen.**
PHARMACOLOGICAL AND CLINICAL ASPECTS OF PHOSPHODIESTERASE TYPE 5
INHIBITORS IN THE TREATMENT OF ERECTILE DYSFUNCTION.....439

CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY

62. **Saidova A. Shakhnoza, Musayeva J. Lola, Pulatova I. Nargiza, Pulatova B. Durdona, Abdusamatova Z. Dilorom, Avazova N. Gulchekhra.**
CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY OF MINERALOCORTICOID RECEPTOR
ANTAGONISTS AND THEIR USE IN TREATMENT OF INTERNAL DISEASE
PATHOLOGY.....451

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
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A NUMBER OF ERRORS IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF ACUTE APPENDICITIS IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

In modern medicine, numerous studies are conducted to improve the quality of diagnosis of acute appendicitis, especially in the early stages of its development. The reasons for errors in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis, as in our clinical examples, are the absence of a pathognomonic sign of acute appendicitis and the presence of clinical signs and symptoms characteristic of both acute diarrheal infection.

Key words: acute appendicitis, appendicular peritonitis, children, clinical symptoms.

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РЯД ОШИБОК ПРИ ДИАГНОСТИКЕ ОСТРОГО АППЕНДИЦИТА У ДЕТЕЙ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В современной медицине проводятся многочисленные исследования для повышения качества диагностики острого аппендицита, особенно на ранних стадиях его развития. Причиной ошибок при диагностике острого аппендицита, как и в наших клинических примерах, являются отсутствие патогномичного признака острого аппендицита и наличие клинических признаков и симптомов, характерных как для острой диарейной инфекции.

Ключевые слова: острый аппендицит, аппендикулярный перитонит, дети, клинические симптомы.

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**BOLALARDA O'TKIR APPENDITSITNI TASHXISLASHDA BIR QATOR
XATOLIKLAR****ANNOTATSIYA**

Zamonaviy tibbiyotda o'tkir appenditsitni tashxislash sifatini yaxshilash uchun ko'plab tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda, ayniqsa uning rivojlanishining dastlabki bosqichlarida o'tkir appenditsitni tashxislashda xatolarning sabablari, bizning klinik misollarimizda bo'lgani kabi, o'tkir appenditsitning patognomonik belgisining yo'qligi va o'tkir diareya infeksiyasiga xos bo'lgan klinik belgilar va alomatlarining mavjudligida.

Kalit so'zlar: o'tkir appendisit, appendikulyar peritonit, bolalar, klinik belgilar.

INTRODUCTION: Differential diagnosis of such diseases as acute appendicitis and acute intestinal infection in children is an urgent problem affecting the field of activity of both surgeon and pediatrician. Undiagnosed appendicitis leads to the development of complicated forms of appendix inflammation, which prolongs surgical intervention and the duration of antibiotic therapy, increasing the hospital stay of the child. Our study demonstrates the need for multidisciplinary approach and comprehensive diagnosis of patients with complaints such as abdominal pain, fever and diarrhea. Abdominal pain is the most common reason for presenting to the emergency department and is most commonly caused by an attack of acute appendicitis. However, there is a high chance of misdiagnosis of acute appendicitis due to unusual symptoms. Therefore, the physician must be very careful in making the correct diagnosis. Despite the large number of works devoted to acute appendicitis and its complications in children, the incidence of premature diagnosis of acute surgical pathology remains high. Acute appendicitis continues to be disguised as acute intestinal infections [1]. The similarity of clinical symptoms in inflammation of the appendix and infectious diseases of the gastrointestinal tract significantly complicates timely diagnosis and correct diagnosis [2]. Untimely diagnosis of surgical complications in children can have irreparable consequences due to the development of neglected forms of peritonitis, which are manifested by endotoxic shock and multi-organ failure syndrome [3]. The lifetime risk of developing appendicitis is 8.6% for men and 6.7% for women, and the overall prevalence worldwide is 7%. The incidence of acute appendicitis has steadily declined since the late 1940s, and the current annual incidence is 10 cases per 100,000 population. In Asian and African countries, the incidence of acute appendicitis is probably lower because of the dietary habits of the inhabitants of these geographic regions. Dietary fiber is thought to reduce the viscosity of fecal matter, shorten its transit time through the intestine, and prevent the formation of fecal matter that can cause obstruction of the lumen of the worm [4].

Among adolescents and young adults, there is a slight preponderance of males - 3: 2. In adults, the incidence of appendicitis in men is about 1.4 times higher than in women. However, many studies have shown a predominance of female patients over male patients. The incidence of primary appendectomy is about the same in both sexes [5]. The incidence of appendicitis gradually increases from birth, peaks in late adolescence and gradually decreases in old age. The average age of appendicitis development among children is 6-10 years. Lymphoid hyperplasia is more common in infants and young adults and is responsible for the increased incidence of appendicitis in these age groups. Young children have a higher chance of perforation, 50-85%. The average age of appendectomy is 22 years. Hence, clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion in all age groups [6]. The worm is not fixed. While its base occupies a fairly constant location, the free end may change position: extending into the retroperitoneum, descending into the pelvis, or located behind the blind colon. The prevalence of different locations of the worm is significantly varies in the population.

Thus, retrocecal location of the appendix is common in Ghana and Sudan (67.3 and 58.3%, respectively), in Iran and Bosnia, pelvic location is the most common (55.8 and 57.7% of episodes, respectively). In very rare cases (laparotomy with suspected appendicitis incidence 1:100000), the worm is absent. Sometimes there is a semicircular fold of mucosa at the mouth of the appendix - the valve of the worm or Gerlach's flap. The etiology of acute appendicitis at the current stage of medical development is not fully understood. Most scientists believe that obstruction of the lumen of the worm is the leading cause of this disease [3]. Fecal stones and lymphoid hyperplasia are the main causes of obstruction. Also, obstruction is a key cause of appendicitis progression, but data on fecaliths as the most frequent cause of uncomplicated appendicitis are scarce. Overall, fecaliths were found in 18.1% of appendiceal specimens and 28.6% of negative appendectomies. Fecaliths are more common in perforative than in uncomplicated acute appendicitis. Also, fecaliths are more common in pediatric than adult population, regardless of whether it is perforative [4].

The lumen distal to the obstruction begins to fill with mucus and acts as a closed circuit obstruction. This leads to distension and increased intraluminal and intramural pressure. As the disease progresses, resident bacteria in the appendix multiply rapidly [7]. Dilation of the appendix lumen causes reflex anorexia, nausea and vomiting, and visceral pain. When the lumen pressure exceeds venous pressure, the small venules and capillaries thrombose, but the arterioles remain open, leading to appendiceal engorgement and obstruction. The inflammatory process soon involves the serous membrane of the appendix, hence the parietal peritoneum in this area, causing classic right lower quadrant (RLQ) pain. Once the small arterioles are thrombosed, the area at the antimesenteric border becomes ischemic, leading to infarction and perforation. Bacteria migrate through the necrotized walls, and pus forms in and around the appendix. Perforation is usually seen just behind the obstruction and not at the end of the appendix [3]. Appendicitis in children is the most common abdominal disease requiring surgical intervention in this age group. The lifetime risk of developing appendicitis is 8.7% for boys and 6.7% for girls. The incidence of misdiagnosis ranges from 28-57% in children between 2 and 12 years of age and approaches almost 100% in children younger than 2 years of age [8].

In early childhood, the manifestations of acute appendicitis are atypical, making diagnosis difficult. In addition, children in this age group have poor communication skills, which may lead to misunderstanding of the disease process. The different clinical presentation in different age groups is well explained by anatomical and pathophysiologic differences. These factors are of great concern to clinicians and emphasize the need for proper evaluation of these patients for successful treatment.

Newborns.

This group of children is characterized by the highest probability of acute appendicitis [1]. Obturation of the lumen of the process is not the leading mechanism of acute appendicitis development. Thrombotic embolism, internal or external hernia obturation, cardiac abnormalities, and distal colon obstruction, as in Hirschsprung's disease, take precedence.

At this age, pain and nausea should not be considered as the main symptoms of the disease. This age group is more characterized by abdominal bloating in 60% to 90%, vomiting in 59%, palpable mass in 20-40%, crying or lethargy in 22% and 12-16% with symptoms of peritoneal irritation. However, hypotension, hypothermia, right hip stiffness and respiratory distress were also observed in some cases [8].

Prominent symptoms of Children under 3 years of age.

in this age group are vomiting (85% to 90%), pain (35% to 81%), fever (40% to 60%), and diarrhea (18% to 46%). Other common symptoms in this age group are irritability (35% to 40%), cough or rhinitis (40%), wheezing (8% to 23%), restricted right hip mobility, pain, and claudication in 3 to 23%. Vomiting and irritability are also symptoms of many other conditions at this age, such as gastroenteritis, mesenteric adenitis, intussusception, otitis media, and upper respiratory tract infections. On physical examination, most children (87% to 100%) have fever above 37°C and diffuse abdominal tenderness (55% to 92%); whereas localized right lower quadrant tenderness is seen in less than 50% of cases. Other notable signs are lethargy, drowsiness, crying (40%), abdominal bloating (30-52%), diarrhea or constipation (23%), and a mass palpated through the abdominal wall

or rectum (30%) [9]. Because the manifestations of acute appendicitis in this age group are nonspecific and vague, the average time interval between the onset of symptoms and final diagnosis is usually 3-4 days. This delay in diagnosis most often leads to perforation (82-92%) and bowel obstruction in 82% .

Preschool (age 3-5 years)

The incidence of acute appendicitis in this age group is low, accounting for less than 5% of all appendicitis in children [2]. Children's communication skills improve as they get older and they are able to talk about their concerns, which means that early diagnosis of acute appendicitis becomes easier and more accurate. Most children in this age group present with complaints within the last two days, and up to 17% have symptoms for more than 6 days before a definitive diagnosis is made [4]. In this age group, the most common symptom is abdominal pain (89% to 100%), followed by vomiting (66 to 100%), fever (80 to 87%), and anorexia (53 to 60%). On examination, localized right lower quadrant soreness (58% to 85%) predominates over diffuse soreness (19% to 28%). Other physical signs include involuntary and painful urination (85%) and temperature above 37.5°C (82%) .

Causes of misdiagnosis and higher incidence of perforation

The nonspecific clinical presentation in children younger than 5 years of age, as well as difficulty in communicating with them, inadequate physical examination, crying, and overlap of symptoms with other common childhood illnesses are the reasons for the late diagnosis of acute appendicitis and high probability of misdiagnosis. Consequently, they are more likely to develop complications such as perforation and abscess formation. Other factors contributing to perforation are thin-walled outflow tract and inadequate omental barrier. The differential diagnosis in these children includes but is not limited to acute gastroenteritis, upper and lower respiratory tract infections, urinary tract infections, cholecystitis, constipation, intussusception, pelvic inflammatory disease, blunt abdominal trauma, abscessed hernia, testicular torsion, orchitis, nephrolithiasis, septic arthritis of the right hip, dehydration, sepsis, encephalopathy, and meningitis. The overall rate of missed diagnosis ranges from 70 to 100% among children 3 years of age and younger, 19 to 57% in the preschool age group (with perforation in 43-72% of cases). This rate decreases to 12-28% in school-aged children, reaching less than 15% in adolescents [6].

In a clinical study, up to 15% of patients were seen twice or more in the emergency department before a diagnosis of acute appendicitis was made, and common features for misdiagnosed patients were relatively short duration of symptoms at the first visit, most of them visited the emergency department at night, had fewer physical findings on examination, and were not well screened [4]. The incidence of misdiagnosis increases with age, and in young children, the risk of complicated appendicitis increases 5-fold. In a study involving 102 children in which researchers examined risk factors for worm perforation, it was found that duration of pain and presence of a mass were the most statistically significant factors [2].

Objective of the study. Retrospective study to examine the errors of different surgeons in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in children

Materials and Methods of the Study. Our study included 30 children aged 2 to 10 years hospitalized in an infectious disease department with acute intestinal infection during nine months in 2020. The reason for hospitalization was the presence of symptoms in patients to suspect an infectious disease. A retrospective review of patient records was conducted; the study complied with ethical standards and individual patient data were not disclosed. The etiological structure, incidence and clinical characteristics of acute appendicitis hiding behind the mask of acute intestinal infection were analyzed. Statistical analysis and data processing were performed using standard Statistica 10 program with determination of mean values.

Results of the study

The study included 10 girls (33.3%), 20 boys (66.7%), the average age of the patients was 7.3 years. In the observed group, the proportion of children under 3 years old was 13.4% (four children), from 3 to 5 years old - 33.3% (10), 53.3% (16 children). All hospitalized patients presented complaints of abdominal pain and stool disorders. In addition, 11 (36.7%) patients had nausea and vomiting.

Most of the patients were hospitalized on the first (15 patients, 50%), second (8 patients, 26.7%) and third (6 patients, 20%) day after the onset of the disease. One (3.33) patient was hospitalized on the fourth day. The differential diagnosis revealed surgical and urologic diseases. The patients were transferred to specialized departments. In surgical pathology of this age group acute appendicitis prevailed - 7 cases of the disease, urologic diseases were diagnosed in 5 children. The peculiarity of the clinical picture of patients with surgical pathology is a slight increase in temperature (up to a maximum of 37.4 ° C), the location of pain in the epigastric and umbilical regions, the presence of exacerbation of pain syndrome, diarrhea. It was also characterized by increased intensity of the pain syndrome and an increase in the number of leukocytes in the peripheral blood in the first hours after hospitalization.

1. Boys (66.7%) were predominant in the study group, the average age was 7, 3 years.
2. In the observed group the specific weight of children under 3 years old was 13,4% (four children), from 3 to 5 years old - 33,3% (ten children), 53,3% (16 children).
3. the majority of patients were hospitalized on the first day (50%).
4. Acute appendicitis was diagnosed in 7 children (23.3%), urologic diseases in 5 children (16.7%).

Conclusions: Thus, the reasons for errors in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis, are the absence of pathognomonic signs of acute appendicitis and the presence of clinical signs and symptoms characteristic of both acute diarrheal infection and acute abdominal surgical pathology.

The reason for making a wrong diagnosis in all cases was abdominal pain of atypically localized localization. However, if in acute intestinal infections diagnostic errors lead to incorrect treatment and unnecessary surgical intervention, in case of untimely recognition of acute appendicitis its complicated forms develop, there is a threat of endotoxic shock, multi-organ failure. All this significantly complicates the postoperative period, requires large expenses for rehabilitation, and in neglected situations can lead to death.

It is important to remember, especially for novice doctors, both pediatricians and surgeons, that in case of doubtful diagnosis or suspicion of acute appendicitis, the child is placed under round-the-clock observation in the hospital in the surgical department. If there is no effect of conservative therapy aimed at treating intestinal infection, it is necessary to combine instrumental and laboratory methods of investigation in dynamics and expand the indications for diagnostic laparoscopy. This will prevent misdiagnosis and avoid complicated forms of appendicitis in children.

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